

Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-chlorophenyl-o-chlorobenzamidine Hydrochloride and Thiocyanate⁺

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N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-chlorophenyl-o-chlorobenzamidine hydrochloride (HPCPCBH) is a newly synthesised reagent which reacts with vanadium(V) in presence of thiocyanate forming a green coloured water insoluble ternary complex quantitatively extractable into chloroform and shows λ_{max} in the region 600-620 nm. The extractibility can be explained on the basis of the formation of 1 : 2 : 2 (metal : HPCPCBH : SCN^-) ternary species which is hydrophobic in nature. The method based on the sensitive colour reaction is fairly selective. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $4713 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.018 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$ of V(V), respectively. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 20 to 240 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$. The applicability of the method is tested in BCS steel.

VARIOUS reagents¹⁻¹¹ have been recommended for extractive photometric determination of V(V).

On the other hand N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-chlorophenyl-o-chlorobenzamidine hydrochloride (HPCPCBH) is advantageous because it is sensitive and selective and free from many of the drawbacks of the other reagents.

Experimental

The spectra were recorded with Carl-Zeiss UV-VIS Specord spectrophotometer. pH was recorded with a Systronic pH meter, type 322.

Stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared by dissolving 1.14822 g ammonium metavanadate in 1 litre. It was standardised volumetrically. An aqueous solution (1% w/v) of potassium thiocyanate (AnalaR grade) was used.

Preparation of HPCPCBH : The reagent was prepared by condensation of equimolecular quantities of N-p-chlorophenyl-o-chlorobenzamidoyl chloride and N-phenylhydroxylamine in ether. The resulting hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute alcohol. A 0.1% solution of HPCPCBH in chloroform was used for extraction purposes.

Procedure : An aliquot of V(V) solution containing $100 \mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ metal was placed in a separating funnel. The aqueous phase was made to 25 ml by adding 2 M HCl for adjusting to the required pH and 5 ml of 1% potassium thiocyanate. V(V) was extracted with 25 ml of 0.1% chloroform solution of HPCPCBH. The absorbance of the coloured species was measured at the wavelength of maximum absorption against chloroform blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The complex absorbed strongly at 600-620 nm at which HPCPCBH showed negligible absorbance (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra.
A $\circ-\circ$ V(V)-HPCPCBH- SCN^-
B $\bullet-\bullet$ V(V)-HPCPCBH
C $\times-\times$ 0.1% w/v HPCPCBH in chloroform

Nature of the complex : The stoichiometry of the metal : reagent : thiocyanate was examined by curve fitting method. The result indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 : 2 ternary complex.

Effect of variables : The optimum acidity range was found to be pH 1 to 3.5. In this system 6 fold

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molar excess of HPCPCBH and 5 fold excess of thiocyanate were adequate for complete extraction.

Effect of substituents : The substitution resulted into hyperchromic shift, the order being $p\text{-chloro} = m\text{-chloro} = p\text{-tolyl} = m\text{-tolyl} > \text{H}$ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF VANADIUM(V)-THIOCYANATE COMPLEXES WITH HYDROXYAMIDINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN CHLOROFORM

Sl. No.	Y	λ_{max} (nm)	$l. \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$
1.	H	620	4713	0.0180
2.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	620	5350	0.0090
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	620	5350	0.0090
4.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	620	5350	0.0090
5.	<i>m</i> -tolyl	620	5300	0.0089

Effect of diverse ions : Extraction of V(V) was carried in the presence of known quantity of diverse ions. Fluoride, chloride, bromide, phosphate, arsenate, tartrate do not interfere. The limit for some metal ions in ppm are given in parenthesis : Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} (600); Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (2000); Al^{3+} (2700); Cr^{3+} (2000); Fe^{3+} (1700); in the presence of trisodium phosphate, Mn^{2+} (700); Zr^{4+} (200); Mo^{6+} (250); W^{6+} (20); Cu^{2+} (250).

Molar absorptivity, sensitivity, Beer's law, optimum concentration range and precision : The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity^{1,2} are $4713 l. \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.018 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of V(V). The optimum concentration range on the basis of Ringbom^{1,3} plot is 40 to 200 μg metal per 25 ml.

Application of the method : The validity of the method was tested with two tungsten vanadium steel (64a and 241/1) and a tungsten free alloy steel (252). The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN BCS* STEEL

Sl. No.	Steel sample	Found (f) %	Certified value %	Standard deviation
1.	64a Alloy steel	1.56	1.57	± 0.0084
2.	241/1 High speed steel	1.551	1.57	± 0.0046
3.	252 Low alloy steel	0.448	0.46	± 0.0083

*British Chemical Standard, Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks.

(f) Mean of five samples.

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